

An Investigation of the Role of Promotional Tactics in Impulsive Purchasing, in Online Shopping with a Focus on Sivakasi

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Abstract

An impulse purchase or impulse buying is an unplanned decision by a consumer to buy a product or service, made just before a purchase. One who tends to make such purchases is referred to as an impulse purchaser or impulse buyer. This study examines the relationship between advertisement and impulsive buying frequency in online marketplaces with special reference to online users. This research analyzes the role of promotional tactics and online impulsive buying. The study employed non-probability sampling, and responses from 300 online users were analyzed. Statistical tools such as Chi-square test and ANOVA were used to interpret the findings.

Keywords: Advertisement, Impulsive Buying, Online Shopping.

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Introduction

Impulsive buying is the tendency of a customer to buy goods and services without planning in advance. When a customer takes such buying decisions at the spur of the moment, it is usually triggered by emotions and feelings. Impulsive buying can't be categorized for one specific product category. Impulsive buying can be seen in products such as chocolates, clothes, mobile phones and in big-ticket items such as cars, jewelry etc. Impulsive buying means making an unplanned purchase. It is based on an irrational thinking. Marketers try to tap this behavior of customers to boost sales. There is a great likelihood that customers end up making a purchase of products after entering the hypermarket without any actual intent of doing so. A common reason for impulse buying is the fear of missing out on a good deal, such as an item that's on promotion or is limited time only. This sense of urgency causes the shopper to act on the assumption that they'll miss out if they don't act now and make an immediate purchase.

Impulsive Buying and Advertisement:

The definition of advertising is an industry used to call the attention of the public to something, typically a product or service. An advertisement, otherwise known as an advert or ad, is generally considered a public communication that promotes a product, service, brand or event. Advertisements are important for businesses because they are the most direct and proven way to reach potential customers. Advertisement plays a big role in business related to impulsive buying. Advertising can create desire for a product, service, or idea by using persuasive language, imagery, and other techniques. This can influence people's behavior by encouraging them to purchase or engage with the product, service, or idea.

Statement of the problem:

In the past, shopping was only done offline. Customers may visit the store, look through the pictures, and buy the goods. However, due to the increased availability of online shopping platforms and the growing usage of technology, shopping may now shift from offline to online. Marketers might employ several strategies to draw clients to those platforms, such as promotions, discounts, buy one, get one free deal, and eye-catching visuals. As a result of

increased accessibility brought about by technological advancements, consumers may make purchases online without careful forethought. Since there are more online buyers in Sivakasi, the study will concentrate on examining how promotional strategies affect impulsive purchases made online.

Review of literature:

Tech savvy millennials are always in hunt to get the best deal as and when required. They seek instant gratification in everything i.e from information to shopping, to eating to entertainment (NM Rani, 2020) Impulsive buying is characterized by sudden and immediate purchases without any prior intention to shop, either for specific product categories or to fulfill specific purchasing tasks (Beatty and Ferrell as cited in (Deshpande, 2021). Parboteeah (cited in Nagadeepa, 2021) defines impulsive buying as an unplanned purchase triggered by a stimulus and made on the spot. Following the purchase, customers often undergo emotional and/or cognitive reactions. There are several indicators of impulsive buying according to Herlina and Widyaningrum (2022), which include: 1. Irresistible Urge to Buy: This condition occurs when consumers have an instant and persistent desire, leading them to be unable to resist the urge to make a purchase. 2. Positive Buying Emotion: This is when consumers experience joy and satisfaction from making impulsive purchases. 3. Consumer Mood Management: This refers to the consumer's desire to change their mood through impulsive buying. 4. Cognitive Deliberation: This is a state where potential consumers feel a strong urge to act without considering the consequences. 5. Unplanned Buying: This occurs when consumers shop without a clear plan. 6. Disregard for Future: This condition happens when consumers make impulsive purchases without considering future implications. Internet is a very convenient and economical channel for promotional campaigns by the marketers and provides a vibrant platform for the buyers to buy things online. Impulsive buying is a kind of purchase behavior that is not controlled by emotion (Zhang M, Shi G, 2022). Predicting consumer behavior completely is highly complex phenomenon; however, new research approaches, such as consumer neuroscience have shed light on how consumers make their decisions (Dawood, T. H et al, 2022). Prasad K et al (2022) summarized that substantial research has been done as to the most prominent factors influencing the customers' perceived value and the same may broadly be classified as utilitarian factors, such as ease of use, usefulness, informativeness, and hedonic factors that include perceived enjoyment, fun, fantasy and playfulness. Predicting consumer behavior completely is highly complex phenomenon;

however, new research approaches, such as consumer neuroscience have shed light on how consumers make their decisions (**Dawood, T. H et al, 2022**). The flow experience is also effective in fostering positive emotions in individuals. Those who achieve certain internal goals and overcome challenges during this process feel active and motivated. Regardless of the type of activity, it has been observed that the flow experience enhances a sense of discovery and quality of life, making individuals feel more joyful and happy (**Sağtaş et al., 2023**). Promotion fundamentally aims to increase the number of new customers, influence customers to try new products, encourage more purchases, counter competitors' promotional activities, boost impulse buying, or foster closer cooperation with resellers (**Ratnasariet al., 2023**). Marketers capitalize on consumers' emotional responses, thereby increasing the likelihood of impulsive purchases through emotional contagion (**Herdiana & Supriyono, 2023**). Impulse buying is caused by two factors. External factors are the emergence of market, display, and availability of money and time. Internal factors come from a person's personality, failure of self-control and personal pleasure (**Harahap et al., 2023**). Users are visually influenced by various product photographs published on e-commerce platforms, which strategically aim to stimulate purchases (**Mohapatra et al., 2024**). 12 studies examine the impact of limited-time discounts, such as flash sales and temporary offers, on consumer decision-making and impulsive buying behavior. **Keenan (2024)** defines sales promotion as a marketing activity that can increase sales, encourage repeat purchases, create brand awareness.

Scope of the study:

The research aims to study the promotional tactics adopted by marketers in online shopping and impulsive buying behavior on online users in the context of buying the products. The respondents would be selected from gender, different age groups, regarding purchasing the product. The study focuses only on the online shopping users only.

Objectives of the study:

1. To know the socioeconomic profile of the online shoppers in Sivakasi.
2. To identify the factors that influence impulsive buying through online shopping.
3. To find out the various payment options to encourage the purchase decision of the online shoppers.
4. To highlight the visual ads and images that can increase the online shopping habits.

5. To give suggestions for improving the attraction of appeals to increase the sales for online platforms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Through the investigation of research methodologies, the research procedure is a practical evaluation aimed at providing answers for logical and social concerns. It is a methodical approach to assess the result by planning and decomposing the problem via the application of various techniques and systems. The test-taking techniques are well-organized, rational, and value-neutral. Statistics and descriptive analysis will be used in the survey. A questionnaire given to 300 respondents who had made an impulsive buying provided the primary data. The survey was sent as a Google form through the What's App Group. Since non probability sampling was the sampling strategy employed in this investigation.

Statistical Tools:

The data collected through Google Forms were analyzed using

1. Simple Percentage analysis
2. Chi-square test
3. ANOVA

Collection of data:

The research incorporates both primary and secondary data. The primary data has been gathered from the respondents using Google forms. Secondary data has been obtained from diverse sources, including publications, unpublished reports, journals, and articles, etc.

Hypotheses:

H1: There is no significant relationship between socio economic profile of the respondents and the factors influence the impulsive buying behavior.

H2: There is no significant relationship between age of the respondents and common impulse buying products for customers during the online purchases.

Limitations of the study:

1. The study covers a period of 3 months
2. Due to shortage of time and other constraints the study has been limited to 300 respondents only.
3. The data collected for the research is fully on primary data given by the respondent.
4. Findings of the study are based on the assumptions that the respondents have given correct information.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1
Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents

Socio-Economic Profile		No. of Respondents	Percentage
Gender	Male	174	58
	Female	126	42
Age (in years)	Below 20	21	7.00
	Between 21-25	97	32.33
	Between 26-30	127	42.33
	Between 31-35	42	14.00
	Above 35	13	4.33
Literacy	Illiterate	7	2.33
	School level	91	30.33
	Graduate level	142	47.33
	Post Graduate level	33	11.00
	Others	27	9.00
Occupation	Private Employee	120	40.00
	Government Employee	47	15.67
	Self Employed	43	14.33
	Professional	81	27.00
	House wife	9	3.00
Monthly Income (in Rs.)	Below 5,000	13	4.33
	5,001 –10,000	87	29.00
	10,001 –15,000	94	31.33
	15,001 –20,000	77	25.67
	Above 20,000	29	9.67

Source: Primary data

Regrading gender wise classification, out of 300 respondents, 174 (58%) are male and the remaining 126 (42%) are female.

Regarding age wise classification, out of 300 respondents, 127 (42.33%) belong to the age group of 26-30 years, 97 (32.33%) come under the age group of 21-25 years, 42 (14%) fall under the age group of 31-35 years, 21 (7%) are in the age group of below 20 years and 13 (4.33%) belong to the age group above 35 years.

Regarding education wise classification, out of 300 respondents, 142 (47.33%) are graduates, 91 (30.33%) have finished their education upto school level, 33 (11%) are post graduates, 27 (9%) belong to others category (certificate/diploma holders) and 7 (2.33%) are illiterates.

Regarding occupation wise classification, out of 300 respondents, 120 (40%) are private employees, 81 (27%) are professionals, 47 (15.67%) are Government employees, 43 (14.33%) are self-employed and 9 (3%) are house wives.

Regarding monthly income wise classification, 94 (31.33%) have earned Rs. 10,001 – Rs. 15,000 per month, 87 (29%) have earned Rs. 5,001 – Rs. 10,000 per month, 77 (25.67%) have earned Rs. 15,001 – Rs. 20,000 per month, 29 (9.67%) have earned above Rs. 20,000 per month and 13 (4.33%) have earned below Rs. 5,000 per month.

Table 2
Profile of Online Shopping

Profile of Online Shopping		No. of Respondents	Percentage
Frequency of online shopping	Rarely	53	17.67
	Monthly	124	41.33
	Daily	39	13.00
	Weekly	80	26.67
	Never	4	1.33
Digital Payment mode used for online shopping	Pay tm and phone pe	112	37.33
	Internet banking services	67	22.33
	Debit and credit cards	87	29.00
	AEPS	34	11.33

Source: Primary data

Regarding frequency of online shopping, 124 (41.33%) have made online shopping monthly, 80 (26.67%) have done online shopping weekly, 53 (17.67%) have rarely made online shopping, 39 (13%) have done online shopping daily and 4 (1.33%) have never made online shopping.

Regarding digital payment mode used for online shopping, 112 (37.33%) have used paytm and phone pe, 87 (29%) have used debit and credit cards, 67 (22.33%) have used internet banking services and 34 (11.33%) have used AEPS.

Table 3
Factors influence the Impulsive Buying Behaviour

Factors	Rank					Total
	I	II	III	IV	V	
Convenience	87	73	54	52	34	300
Speed	69	75	88	13	55	300
Security	33	63	42	58	104	300
Cost Effectiveness	12	74	76	85	53	300
Technological advancement	99	15	40	92	54	300
Total	300	300	300	300	300	

Source: Primary data

Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents and Factors influence the Impulsive Buying Behaviour – Chi Square Test

Chi square test has been used to examine the relationship between socio economic profile of the respondents and the factors influence the impulsive buying behavior. The null hypothesis framed is that there is no significant relationship between socio economic profile of the respondents and the factors influence the impulsive buying behavior.

Table 4
Socio-Economic Profile of the Respondents and Factors influence the Impulsive Buying Behaviour – Chi Square Test

	Calculated value	P value
Gender and Convenience	24.026	0.000
Gender and Speed	9.458	0.004
Gender and Security	9.115	0.003
Gender and Cost Effectiveness	12.102	0.011
Gender and Technological advancement	11.172	0.528
Age and Convenience	9.576	0.001
Age and Speed	6.503	0.438
Age and Security	8.103	0.003

Age and Cost Effectiveness	11.122	0.017
Age and Technological advancement	9.409	0.000
Education and Convenience	17.810	0.025
Education and Speed	20.108	0.018
Education and Security	31.182	0.011
Education and Cost Effectiveness	6.927	0.000
Education and Technological advancement	27.811	0.003
Occupation and Convenience	22.124	0.001
Occupation and Speed	19.357	0.004
Occupation and Security	4.248	0.268
Occupation and Cost Effectiveness	7.068	0.016
Occupation and Technological advancement	6.214	0.000
Monthly Income and Convenience	11.091	0.314
Monthly Income and Speed	17.235	0.127
Monthly Income and Security	21.385	0.105
Monthly Income and Cost Effectiveness	12.004	0.000
Monthly Income and Technological advancement	9.374	0.238

Source: Primary data

- Regarding gender, the factor technological advancement is not significant as its p value is more than 0.05.
- Regarding age, the factor speed is not significant as its p value is more than 0.05.
- Regarding education, all the factors are significant as their p values are less than 0.05.
- Regarding occupation, the factor security is not significant as its p value is more than 0.05.
- Regarding monthly income, the factor cost effectiveness is only significant and the other four factors are not significant.

Table 5
Common Impulsive Buying Products

Products	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Food and Groceries	35	11.67
Shoes.	17	5.67
Takeout and Delivery.	12	4.00
Beauty Products. .	55	18.33
Books.	48	16.00
Magazines and Newspapers	10	3.33
Toys for Kids.	45	15.00
House hold articles	10	3.33
Home Decor	24	8.00
Gadgets and devices	19	6.33
Software apps	13	4.33
Jewellery	7	2.33
Video games	5	1.67
Total	300	100.00

Source: Primary data

Out of 300 respondents, 55 (18.33%) have bought beauty products, 48 (16%) have bought books, 45 (15%) have bought toys for kids, 35 (11.67%) have bought food and groceries, 24 (8%) have bought home décor articles, 19 (6.33%) have bought gadgets and devices, 17(5.67%) have bought shoes, 13 (4.33%) have bought software apps, 12 (4%) have bought take out and delivery products, 10 (3.33%) have bought magazines and newspapers, another 10 (3.33%) have bought household articles, 7 (2.33%) have bought jewellery and 5 (1.67%) have bought video games.

Relationship between frequency of online shopping and Common Impulsive Buying Products

Chi Square test has been used to examine the relationship between frequency of online shopping and common impulsive buying products. The null hypothesis framed is that there is no significant relationship between frequency of online shopping and common impulsive buying products.

Table 6
Relationship between frequency of online shopping and
Common Impulsive Buying Products

Calculated value	101.582
Table value	64.80
Degrees of Freedom	$(13-1) (5-1) = 12*4 = 48$
Level of significance	95%
P value	0.000
Result	Significant

Source: Primary data

As the calculated value of Chi Square test (101.582) is significant as its p value is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) and the calculated value is more than the table value, the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, it is proved that there is a significant relationship between frequency of online shopping and common impulsive buying products.

Table 7
Social and psychological factors that affect your impulsive purchases

Variables		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Total
Enjoyment.	Count	166	111	7	12	4	300
	%	55.33	37.00	2.33	4.00	1.33	100.00
Fear of losing the moment.	Count	111	152	33	3	1	300
	%	37.00	50.67	11.00	1.00	0.33	100.00
Sale	Count	116	110	53	14	7	300
	%	38.67	36.67	17.67	4.67	2.33	100.00
Addictions and habits.	Count	107	93	52	24	24	300
	%	35.67	31.00	17.33	8.00	8.00	100.00
Stress or anxiety	Count	130	67	73	23	7	300
	%	43.33	22.33	24.33	7.67	2.33	100.00
Price off are provided during off season	Count	97	124	39	25	15	300
	%	32.33	41.33	13.00	8.33	5.00	100.00
After sales service is provided	Count	143	87	29	20	21	300
	%	47.67	29.00	9.67	6.67	7.00	100.00
Free offers are provided	Count	140	73	54	24	9	300
	%	46.67	24.33	18.00	8.00	3.00	100.00

Easy return option is available	Count	157	97	13	20	13	300
	%	52.33	32.33	4.33	6.67	4.33	100.00
Products are available in all sizes.	Count	143	42	57	40	18	300
	%	47.67	14.00	19.00	13.33	6.00	100.00
Heavy advertisement is given for products	Count	129	89	41	12	29	300
	%	43.00	29.67	13.67	4.00	9.67	100.00
Bulk discount is offered.	Count	196	70	12	7	15	300
	%	65.33	23.33	4.00	2.33	5.00	100.00
Purchasing products are delivered by door delivery	Count	102	104	39	30	25	300
	%	34.00	34.67	13.00	10.00	8.33	100.00
Purchasing products through online give instant gratification	Count	169	98	21	6	6	300
	%	56.33	32.67	7.0	2..	2.0	100.00

Source: Primary data

One-way ANOVA test has been used for examining the extent of relationship among Social and psychological factors that affect impulsive purchases of the respondents. The null hypothesis framed is that the social and psychological factors that affect impulsive purchases are not significant.

Table 8
Social and psychological factors that affect your impulsive purchases –
One Way ANOVA Test Results

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Enjoyment	Between Groups	39.163	4	9.791	13.487	.000
	Within Groups	214.157	295	.726		
	Total	253.320	299			
Fear of losing the moment	Between Groups	39.761	4	9.940	11.849	.000
	Within Groups	247.476	295	.839		
	Total	287.237	299			
Sale	Between Groups	31.265	4	7.816	9.879	.000
	Within Groups	233.402	295	.791		
	Total	264.667	299			
Addictions and habits	Between Groups	15.967	4	3.992	2.166	.073
	Within Groups	543.700	295	1.843		
	Total	559.667	299			

Stress or anxiety	Between Groups	53.391	4	13.348	14.805	.000
	Within Groups	265.956	295	.902		
	Total	319.347	299			
Price off are provided during off season	Between Groups	14.073	4	3.518	7.435	.000
	Within Groups	139.593	295	.473		
	Total	153.667	299			
After sales service is provided	Between Groups	26.377	4	6.594	12.025	.000
	Within Groups	161.770	295	.548		
	Total	188.147	299			
Free offers are provided	Between Groups	19.867	4	4.967	7.407	.000
	Within Groups	197.800	295	.671		
	Total	217.667	299			
Easy return option is available	Between Groups	12.374	4	3.094	5.689	.000
	Within Groups	160.413	295	.544		
	Total	172.787	299			
Products are available in all sizes.	Between Groups	31.372	4	7.843	12.687	.000
	Within Groups	182.374	295	.618		
	Total	213.747	299			
Heavy advertisement is given for products	Between Groups	130.406	4	32.602	36.239	.000
	Within Groups	265.391	295	.900		
	Total	395.797	299			
Bulk discount is offered	Between Groups	77.479	4	19.370	19.159	.000
	Within Groups	298.241	295	1.011		
	Total	375.720	299			
Purchasing products are delivered by door delivery	Between Groups	129.046	4	32.261	32.029	.000
	Within Groups	297.141	295	1.007		
	Total	426.187	299			
Purchasing products through online give instant gratification	Between Groups	118.35	4	29.5875	31.69	.000
	Within Groups	275.35	295	0.93339		
	Total	393.7	299			

Source: Primary data

It is interesting to note that all the fourteen variables are significant as its p value is less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). Hence, it is proved that the social and psychological factors that affect impulsive purchases are significant.

Findings of the study:

- 58 percent of the respondents are mostly preferred by male customers for online users.
- 42.33 percent of the respondents belong to the age group of 26-30 years.
- 47.33 percent of the respondents have studied up to aregraduate level of education.
- 40 percent of the respondent's private employees.
- 31.33 percent of the respondents have earned Rs 10,000 – Rs. 15,000 per month
- The analysis shows that *technological advancement* does not differ significantly across gender, as the p-value is greater than 0.05. This indicates that male and female respondents perceive technological advancement similarly.
- The factor *speed* is not significantly associated with different age groups ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that respondents across all ages share a similar opinion regarding the speed of online platforms.
- All the factors studied in relation to education are found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This implies that educational qualification plays an important role in shaping perceptions of online shopping factors.
- The factor *security* is not significantly associated with the occupation of the respondents ($p > 0.05$). Hence, individuals from different occupational groups tend to share similar views about the security features of online shopping.
- Among the factors related to income, only *cost-effectiveness* is significant, whereas the remaining four factors are not significant. This shows that cost-effectiveness varies according to income level, but other factors do not differ much among different income groups.
- There is a significant relationship between frequency of online shopping and common impulsive buying products.
- The One-Way ANOVA test was conducted to examine whether the fourteen variables related to social and psychological factors have a significant effect on impulsive buying behaviour. The results reveal that **all the fourteen variables are statistically significant**, as each variable recorded a p-value less than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$).

Suggestions:

- ❖ Since most of the online users are male under the age groups of 26-30 years, they use their mobile phones for ordering the products through online platforms because

business people may use some tricks to attract the customers for purchasing the product like gorgeous images, discounts, offers etc.

- ❖ Online shopping is increased due to the technological development, and online users are more available and if we go for shopping, you can sit in one place and order the product will come. Another one that is that you return, it means you return the product, so more convenient options are available, so most of us prefer online shopping.

Future Direction for research:

This study spans a period of three months, but in the future, a more thorough investigation should extend close to five months. Only 300 respondents were included in the study; in the future, more respondents will be surveyed. The current study solely looks at online shopping for impulsive purchasing behavior; it does not address which advertisements are most likely to cause impulsive purchases in the future.

Conclusion

Mobile is blurring the Line between Online and Offline Shopping. The biggest impact ecommerce has had on consumer shopping habits is that consumers can shop from anywhere, anytime. They no longer have to wait until store hours to make a purchase.

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